

Sulfur ligand chemistry of mercury and gold : contributions of P. C. Rây and related later developments

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Abstract : The main contributions of Rây in the title area are presented and critically examined in the light of later developments. For mercury the cases examined include $\text{RSHg}(\text{NO}_2)$, $[\text{R}_3\text{S}][\text{HgI}_3]$ and $\text{HgCl}_2(\text{tu})$ (tu = thiourea). The $\text{RSHg}(\text{NO}_2)$ complex is probably a Hg-S-Hg bridged polymer incorporating nitrite 'OO' chelation. The system $[\text{R}_3\text{S}][\text{HgI}_3]$ is particularly noteworthy as $[\text{HgI}_3^-]$ in the R = Me complex is a textbook example of transition metal tricoordination. In $\text{HgCl}_2(\text{tu})$, thiourea is bound in the usual thione form and *not* in the tautomeric thiol form which was invoked by Rây. He pioneered gold(III)-thioether chemistry through the first-ever synthesis and characterization of the family $[\text{Au}(\text{R}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$. His suggestion that $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_2]$ is actually a 'molecular compound' of mono- and tri-valent species was later proven to be essentially correct but in a supramolecular lattice framework.

Keywords : Thiolato mercuric nitrite, triiodomercuric anion, mercury-thiourea system, gold-thioether system, tricoordination, molecular compound.

Introduction

The main research contributions from the laboratory of P. C. Rây can be broadly classified into three main categories. First, chemistry of nitrites which was explored during most of his tenure at Presidency College (1889-1916). Second, thio compounds and their coordination chemistry that received his attention from near the end of the above period through most of his years at the College of Science (1916-1936). Third, chemistry of double sulfates and related species that engaged him in his D.Sc. days in Edinburgh University (1885-1888) and again years later in the College of Science. One item not covered by the above classification is the significant work on fluorination of organic compounds.

Rây was basically a synthetic inorganic chemist. Preparation and characterization of interesting new compounds was the forte of his research. His contributions to nitrite chemistry have recently been chronicled by us¹. As noted therein, characterization tools available then were very few and this greatly handicapped inorganic chemists of the day. Even then Rây was able to make lasting advances in nitrite chemistry where the concerned molecules were relatively simple in nature¹.

His work on the chemistry and coordination chemistry of certain sulfur compounds forms the subject matter of the present article as well as of a subsequent paper of this series. Here the molecular systems prepared turned out to be generally more complex and there were daunting problems of purification, elemental analysis and characterization. He faced these challenges squarely though a few mistakes did creep in here and there. Like in the case of what Prafulla Chandra called triethylene trisulfide, $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{S}_3$, for which the systematic name is 1,4,7-trithiacyclononane (ttcn). In 1920 he claimed the syntheses of ttcn by the reaction of ethylene dibromide with potassium hydrogen sulfide. Later he reported the reactions of the compound with mercury and platinum salts, with ethyl iodide as well as with oxidizing agents^{2,3}. But all this was soon contradicted to the effect that the supposed ttcn was actually the well known 1,4-dithian i.e. 1,4-dithiacyclohexane (dtch), that the reported metal complexes were impure samples and that the oxidation products were those derived from dtch⁴. Rây's defense of his work was rather weak⁵. The mistake was real and was confirmed by others later⁶. Indeed an authentic synthetic route⁷ to ttcn which suffers from large torsional strain

could be achieved only in 1977 with an yield of a mere 0.04%. Routes giving moderate yields were improvised only later. Elemental percentages are the same for ttcn and dtch. Rây's claim in favour of ttcn might have been based⁵ on his elemental analytical data for the metal complexes which however may not have been pure⁴.

But overriding such pitfalls Rây was able to bring about abiding progress in the area and his name is permanently etched in the list of torch bearers in several segments of sulfur-ligand based coordination chemistry specially those of mercury, gold, platinum and iridium. In what follows we shall present salient features of Rây's work on the first two of the four metals. The cases of platinum and iridium will form the subject matter of the next article of the series.

Mercury complexes

Thiol ligands :

Rây initiated work on nitrite chemistry first with mercury¹ and so it was with sulfur-ligand chemistry. His first report in this area appeared in a preliminary note (1914) where he simply stated the formulas he had assigned to the complexes prepared via reaction of mercuric nitrite with a number of 'thio-derivatives' which included ethyl thiol, diethyl sulfide, thioacetamide, thioacetic acid, semicarbazide etc.⁸. No details were given.

The work on thiols (RSH, R = Me, Et) was elaborated two years later^{9,10}. Reaction of a dilute alcoholic solution of RSH with concentrated aqueous $\text{Na}_2[\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_2)_4]$ which acted as the *in situ* precursor of mercuric nitrite, afforded the thiolate complex RSHgNO_2 as a crystalline white or light yellow solid. As elaborated in our earlier paper¹ it is likely that it has a structure based on poly-

meric sulfur-bridged $(-\text{Hg}-\text{SR}-)_n$ chains incorporating nitrite chelation and bridging as depicted in drawing **1** where 'OO' represents nitrite.

The reaction of RSHgNO_2 with excess alkyl iodide (RI) yielded a mixture of nitroalkane (RNO_2) and alkyl nitrite (RONO) and a crystalline yellow compound to which the formula $[\text{R}_2\text{S}_2, \text{HgI}_2, \text{RI}]$ was assigned on the basis of elemental analytical data^{9,10}. Using then-prevalent ideas

Rây proposed for it the structure **2** incorporating an S-S bond between two quadrivalent sulfonium sulfur atoms. Later in a series of papers¹¹ he and his students extended the reaction between mercuric nitrite, various thiols and organic iodides to generate families of compounds supposedly bearing longer sulfur-sulfur chains of the sulfonium type. But the sulfonium chain constitution later ran into serious difficulty and was abandoned.

The events leading to this have been chronicled by us earlier^{12,13} in the case of **2**. In summary, Rây found out that there was an error in his proposed formula of the crystalline yellow compound (correct formula has only one sulfur atom) and that it behaved as uni-univalent electrolyte in acetone solution. He concluded that the compound is a sulfonium salt, $[\text{R}_3\text{S}][\text{HgI}_3]$, which does not involve any Hg-S bonding. Later work by others fully corroborated this. X-Ray work on the R=Me compound has revealed it to have pyramidal $[\text{Me}_3\text{S}]^+$ and planar

tricoordinate $[\text{HgI}_3]^-$ as shown in **3** which remains to this day a model example of the rare phenomenon of tricoordination in transition metal chemistry. For further details refer to the cited papers^{12,13}.

Thiourea ligand :

In 1919 Rây isolated¹⁴ a 1 : 1 complex between mercuric chloride and thiourea (tu) by reacting the two either in ethanol or in water solution. The white precipitate was washed with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*. Its composition

was found to be $\text{HgCl}_2(\text{tu})$. The compound was sparingly soluble in water and the electrical conductivity of its dilute solution corresponded to 1 : 1 electrolytic behaviour¹⁴. The hemihydrate, $\text{HgCl}_2(\text{tu}) \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, prepared by essentially the same procedure but with water washing of the solid was already known¹⁵. Although Rây's work concerned only $\text{HgCl}_2(\text{tu})$, the complexes $\text{HgCl}_2(\text{tu})_2$ and $\text{HgCl}_2(\text{tu})_4$ had also been known for long; $\text{HgCl}_2(\text{tu})_3$ was however reported much later¹⁶.

Rây's main concern with $\text{HgCl}_2(\text{tu})$ was its constitutions, specially the nature of binding of thiourea to the metal atom. He invoked the concept of thione(4a)-thiol(4b) tautomerization and proposed that thione-metal binding as in 4c does not occur and it is the thiol form which binds the metal, the displaced proton being '*fixed*' by a basic nitrogen site as depicted in 4d. He extended this

theme to other metals like copper and platinum and to other sulfur ligands like acetamide and called such ligands as '*potential mercaptans*'¹⁴. Incorporating this theme along with the observation of 1 : 1 electrolytic behaviour in solution, he proposed¹⁴ the constitution 5 for $\text{HgCl}_2(\text{tu})$. We note that he did not specify to which nitrogen the proton was attached; we have chosen it to be the imine nitrogen as in 5.

The proven strong affinity of thiols for mercury may have prompted Rây to invoke the '*potential mercaptan*' theme. But there is another important reason : analogy with the reaction of thiourea with organic halides. Rây himself had studied the reaction of monochloroacetic acid with thiourea at low temperature in 1914¹⁷. The sparingly soluble white solid formed in aqueous media was

considered to be the acid 6a apparently formed via displacement of a molecule of HCl from the reactants and formation of the S- $\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ bond implying that the thiol form of thiourea was active. In acetone solution the reaction afforded the hydrochloride of 6a¹⁷. Later work¹⁸ confirmed Rây's findings. Recent structural data have revealed that the acid actually exists in the zwitterionic form 6b which aggregate into planar sheets that are well-knit via extensive intermolecular N-H...O hydrogen bonding in the lattice¹⁹.

However the hypothesis of metal binding by the thiol tautomer as in 4d has not been substantiated. Indeed thiourea has been found to be invariably bound to mercury in the thione form as in 4c in all complexes of known structure. The X-ray structure of $\text{HgCl}_2(\text{tu})$ itself is not known, but its IR spectrum²⁰ is compatible with a dimeric structure of type 7 incorporating distorted tetrahedral mercury atoms held by a pair of bridging chloride ligands, the

terminal thioether molecules being bonded in mode 4c. Bridge-splitting and chloride dissociation in dilute aqueous solution could explain the observed¹⁴ electrical conductivity.

Interestingly the X-ray structure of a mercuric chloride adduct of formula $\text{HgCl}_2(\text{tu}) \cdot 0.5\text{HgCl}_2$ is known²¹. The $\text{HgCl}_2(\text{tu})$ part defines a polymeric chain with one bridging and one terminal chloride ligand as in 8. The terminal thiourea, bonded as in 4c, completes a distorted tetrahedral coordination sphere around each mercury atom. The 0.5HgCl_2 part represent discrete HgCl_2 molecules (centered on special crystallographic positions) that occupy interstices between the chains of type 8. In conclusion we note that the X-ray structures of the other three

complexes of type $\text{HgCl}_2(\text{tu})_n$ ($n = 2-4$) incorporating bonding type **4c** are known²².

Gold complexes

Introductory comments :

Rây initiated work on gold complexes of sulfur ligands in 1924²³. His objective was to prepare and characterize new variable-valent gold compounds. The inspiration to do so came from his findings in platinum chemistry which he had started a little earlier. He examined the reactions of HAuCl_4 with organic di-, tri- and tetra-sulphides and a dithiol as ligands. The complexes he isolated were mostly multinuclear and had intriguing formulas. He proposed structures based on mere speculation, assigned valency to the metal on that basis and talked of “*bi-, ter-, quadri- and quinque-valent gold compounds*”. He studied the action of coordinating bases like ammonia, pyridine and benzylamine on such compounds and reported the derivatives isolated²⁴. The above phase of his activity^{23,24} cannot be said to have been very fruitful. Time was not yet ripe enough for meaningfully dealing with the complicated coordination chemistry of multisulfur ligands.

Rây's truly significant and lasting contributions to Au-S coordination chemistry emerged after he shifted his focus to mono-sulfur ligands particularly simple thioethers, R_2S , as ligands ($\text{R} = \text{alkyl}$). As chronicled below the activity spanned monovalent and trivalent gold as in $[\text{R}_2\text{SAuCl}]$ and $[\text{R}_2\text{SAuCl}_3]$ respectively²⁵. The third category which apparently corresponded to bivalent gold as in $[\text{R}_2\text{SAuCl}_2]$ was actually a polymerized 1 : 1 molecular compound of the monovalent and trivalent metal in the crystalline state. But it dissociated into the two components in solution. Rây's primary contributions pertained to the trivalent and the mixed-valence entities. One other issue to be considered is the work on thiourea complexation²⁵.

$[\text{Au}(\text{R}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$ and $[\text{Au}(\text{tu})_2\text{Cl}]$:

The first-ever authentic thioether complex of gold appears to be $[\text{Au}(\text{Me}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$ which was reported by Phillips

in 1901²⁶. Prepared by reacting auric chloride with dimethyl thioether this sunlight-sensitive (reduction to metallic gold) crystalline solid is soluble in various organic solvents but the solutions are unstable readily depositing the metal. Later Rây²⁵ isolated the same compound using the above method as well as by reducing the trivalent complex $[\text{Au}(\text{Me}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$ (which he had succeeded to isolate (see below) with warm ethanol). He also prepared thioether complexes similar to $[\text{Au}(\text{Me}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$ in the cases of $(\text{Me})(n\text{-Pr})\text{S}$ and $(\text{PhCH}_2)_2\text{S}$. By reacting $[\text{Au}(\text{Me}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$ with warm pyridine (py) he isolated the complex $[\text{Au}(\text{py})\text{Cl}]$ as a white crystalline solid²⁵.

In $[\text{Au}(\text{R}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$ Rây assigned the coordination number of gold as two but he did not explicitly state the geometry, though his drawing implied angular nature²⁵.

The natural geometry (bicoordinate d^{10} metal ion) is of course linear. An example of X-ray authentication²⁷ is available in the binuclear complex **9** where the average Au-S and Au-Cl distances are 2.26 and 2.31 Å respectively and the two Cl-Au-S angles are 178° and 174° .

Rây synthesized the thiourea (tu) complex of monovalent gold as a white crystalline solid by reacting $[\text{Au}(\text{R}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$ with thiourea in ethanol. He invoked binding by the thiol form $\text{HSC}(\text{NH})(\text{NH}_2)$ as in the case of mercury, *vide supra*, and assigned the formula $[\text{Au}\{\text{SC}(\text{NH})(\text{NH}_2)\}_2\text{Cl}]$ in which the presence of chloride and thiolate-sulfur bound trivalent gold was implicated²⁵. Later it was however shown by others to be a monovalent gold complex incorporating straightforward linear S-Au-S coordination of two thiourea molecules in the usual thione form. The complex is a 1 : 1 electrolytic chloride salt, $[\text{Au}\{\text{SC}(\text{NH}_2)_2\}]\text{Cl}$. This formulation is consistent with IR data²⁸. The X-ray structure of

$[\text{Au}(\text{etu})_2]\text{Cl}$ (etu is ethylenethiourea) has revealed the presence of the nearly linear S-Au-S moiety as in **10** and ionic chloride²⁹.

$[\text{Au}(\text{R}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$:

The first ever successful synthesis and characterization of this family is due entirely to Rây²⁵. It was realized since the work of Phillips²⁶ on synthesis of $[\text{Au}(\text{R}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$ from auric chloride that R_2S acts both as a reducing and a coordinating agent. Though the mechanism of this synthesis was elaborated decades later (see below), Rây intuitively felt²⁵ that if the “*reduction could anyhow be prevented*” it may become feasible to achieve the “*formation of compounds of the type $\text{AuCl}_3 \cdot \text{R}_2\text{S}$* ”. This indeed happened upon adding a strong oxidant like aqua regia or simply nitric acid to sustain the trivalent state of gold. Thus addition of a small amount of aqua regia to an aqueous solution of HAuCl_4 cooled in ice followed by slow addition of an acetone solution of Me_2S afforded yellow crystalline $[\text{Au}(\text{Me}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$. The Et_2S , $n\text{-Pr}_2\text{S}$, $i\text{-Bu}_2\text{S}$, $(\text{Me})(n\text{-Pr})\text{S}$ and Bz_2S ($\text{Bz}=\text{CH}_2\text{Ph}$) homologues were similarly prepared.

Potassium thiocyanate was found to react with $[\text{Au}(\text{R}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$ in the cold liberating R_2S with the formation of $\text{K}[\text{Au}(\text{SCN})_4]$ but the reagent had no appreciable action on $[\text{Au}(\text{R}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$. Also the trivalent complex liberated iodine from potassium iodide while the monovalent complex expectedly failed to do so. The complexes were interconvertible : trivalent to monovalent upon warming in ethanol and monovalent to trivalent upon treatment with chlorine water or dilute aqua regia²⁵.

Rây found the $[\text{Au}(\text{R}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$ complexes monomolecular and nonconducting in freshly prepared acetone solution. He assigned coordination number of the metal as four but did not comment on the geometry. The X-ray structure of the thianthrene complex, **11** has revealed the approximate square planar geometry of AuSCl_3 coordination sphere. The two *trans* Au-Cl lengths are both 2.274 Å while the other Au-Cl distance is longer (2.305 Å) due

to the *trans* influence of the thioether sulfur. The Au-S length is 2.351 Å³⁰.

Later the bromo analogues of $[\text{Au}(\text{R}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$ were reported by others³¹. In far IR the chloro and bromo species display a strong Au-X band in the range 360–355 cm^{-1} and 254–250 cm^{-1} respectively with a shoulder at lower frequency in each case ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$)³². Variable temperature ¹H NMR studies have revealed that the pyramidal sulfur site undergoes spontaneous inversion in both $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$ and $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$, the rate being much faster in the latter³³.

Mechanistic studies³⁴ have revealed that in the first step of the reaction of $[\text{AuCl}_4]^-$ with R_2S a chloride ligand is substituted by SR_2 affording $[\text{Au}(\text{SR}_2)\text{Cl}_3]$. The latter is then attacked by a second SR_2 molecule at the chloride site and not at the metal center. Two halogen atoms are transferred affording SR_2Cl_2 (oxidation) and $[\text{Au}(\text{R}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$ (reduction). The SR_2Cl_2 molecule is promptly hydrolyzed to sulfoxide, R_2SO and hydrogen chloride. That R_2SO is a product of the reaction had been known for long³⁵.

$[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_2]$:

One member that behaves differently from other dialkyl thioethers in the context of gold binding is dibenzyl thioether, Bz_2S . Apart from the usual monovalent and trivalent complexes, white $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$ ^{25,35} and yellow $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$ ²⁵, it afforded the unique orange complex, $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_2]$, deceptively implying the presence of bivalent gold. Originally synthesized by Herrmann in 1905 via the reaction of auric chloride and Bz_2S in diethyl-ether³⁵, its structural nature became the subject of scrutiny by Rây²⁵ and others (see below). Analogous dibromide, diiodide and iodochloride are known³⁶.

Rây found solutions of $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_2]$ to be nonconducting. Earlier Herrmann had found the same³⁵ and later others confirmed this³⁷. This excluded the dimeric ionic structure $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})_2][\text{AuCl}_4]$ where the cation and the anion incorporate monovalent and trivalent gold re-

spectively. Rây proposed that the complex is a 'molecular compound' of monovalent and trivalent entities as in $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$, $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$. He observed that the complex is reconstituted upon recrystallization of an equimolecular mixture of $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$ and $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$ in chloroform. And it is broken down into the constituents upon reaction with KCNS affording $\text{K}[\text{Au}(\text{SCN})_4]$ and Bz_2S (originating from $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$) and $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$ (unreactive to KCNS). Rây's cryoscopic molecular weight (944) was in agreement with the 'molecular compound' formulation²⁵.

Earlier the ebullioscopic molecular weight in chloroform has been reported as 604–608³⁵. However careful cryoscopic work done decades later³⁷ showed that both the reported^{25,35} data were in gross error and the true molecular weight corresponds to the formula $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_2]$. Yet the complex is diamagnetic thus excluding the presence of mononuclear bivalent gold (d^9)³⁷. Finally X-ray structural work revealed the true nature of the compound. It has a one-dimensional polymeric structure of alternate $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$ excluding the presence of monomolecular bivalent gold (d^9)³⁷. Finally X-ray work revealed the true nature of the compound. It has a one-dimensional polymeric structure of alternate $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$ and $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$ held by highly unsymmetrical $\text{Au}^{\text{I}}-\text{Cl}-\text{Au}^{\text{III}}$ bridges ($\text{Au}^{\text{I}}-\text{Cl}$, $\sim 3.6 \text{ \AA}$ and $\text{Au}^{\text{III}}-\text{Cl}$, $\sim 2.1 \text{ \AA}$) as shown schematically in **12**³⁷. It is indeed a polymeric 'molecular compound' or more appropriately, a supramolecular complex in today's parlance. In solution the weak links dissociate and independent monovalent and trivalent species pervade. All observed data are consistent with this. Normally an electrical insulator, the conductivity of **12** in the solid state increases dramatically upon applying large pressures (100–250 Kbar). This has been attributed to the compression along the one-dimensional chains leading to more nearly equivalent coordination environments for the intrachain metal atoms³⁸.

Concluding remarks

In this account we have presented most, if not all, of the important aspects of Rây's work on sulfur-ligand based

coordination chemistry of mercury and gold. The impact of later work by others on the findings and conclusions arrived at by Rây is carefully scrutinized. Among his lasting contributions in the field, the conspicuous items include : (i) correct formulation of the sulfonium salt $[\text{R}_3\text{S}][\text{HgI}_3]$ among which the $\text{R}=\text{Me}$ compound remains a text book example of tricoordination (as in $[\text{HgI}_3]^-$) in transition metal chemistry; (ii) the first-ever successful synthesis and characterization of the family of trivalent gold complexes of thioethers : yellow crystalline $[\text{Au}(\text{R}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$ and (iii) basically correct formulation of $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_2]$ as a molecular compound of $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}]$ and $[\text{Au}(\text{Bz}_2\text{S})\text{Cl}_3]$. Later structural work revealed the linear polymeric disposition of the two entities in the crystal lattice. With the limited facilities available to Rây in Calcutta, his sulfur ligand based studies were beset with problems of purification and characterization and mistakes crept in here and there. But these remain insignificant in the face of the abiding progress he was able to achieve.

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